

holds great promise for both life and non-life insurers.

12. To unleash this potential, insurance companies will need to show long-term commitment to the sector, design products that are suitable for the rural population and utilize appropriate distribution mechanisms.

13. Insurer will have to pay special attention to the characteristics of the rural labour force, like the prevalence of irregular income streams and preference for simple products, before they can successfully penetrate this sector.

14. Insurer will have to maintain continuous contract under the concept of CRM

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04

Analysis of consumer behavior and preferences with respect to AI induced digital marketing

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1: Abstract

The potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in marketing is enormous. It helps to increase the number of information and data sources, enhance the data management capabilities of software, and create complex and sophisticated algorithms. AI is altering how businesses and customers communicate with one another. The type of business and the website's functionality have a big impact on how this technology is used. Marketers may now give customers more of their attention and respond to their requirements immediately. Thanks to the data gathered and produced by its algorithms, AI enables them to swiftly decide what content to target customers with and which channel to use when. When AI is used to personalise user experiences, users are more at ease and more likely to purchase what is being offered.

A kind of artificial intelligence called machine learning (ML) enables computers to analyse and interpret data without having to be explicitly programmed. Additionally, ML helps people solve difficulties effectively. As more data is given into the algorithm, it learns and

becomes more efficient and accurate. Relevant articles on the use of AI in marketing have been found for this study on multiple platforms. Following the reading of these papers, the paper's theme was established. This essay aims to examine consumer behavior and preferences with respect to AI induced digital marketing. An effort is taken to observe what are the reactions of consumers with respect to artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Digital Marketing

2: Introduction

In the long run, Artificial intelligence (AI) will be a crucial component of every business organisation on the planet. Significant changes in the AI landscape are reflected in the latest automation trends led by AI. It is visible in the way that thoughts, interests, and investments have changed in the area of enterprise adoption of AI. Given that this technology is advanced enough to recognise faces and objects, numerous business applications are greatly affected. Facial recognition can be used to identify people for security concerns, whereas object detection can be used to separate and analyse photos. Artificial intelligence (AI) treats human photos like cookies, enabling more individualised services depending on client preferences. Some companies are experimenting with facial recognition to identify their clients' moods and then propose the right products based on that information.

In digital marketing, AI is largely concerned with lead conversion and user retention. With the use of perspective AI chatbots, clever email marketing, interactive web design, and other digital marketing services, it can point a user in the direction that is consistent with the objectives of the company. The effect of AI on digital marketing is dependent on a number of things. A branch of AI called machine learning (ML) is concerned with computer programmes that access data and utilise it to learn on their

own. It gathers information from a variety of sources, including websites, menus, online reviews, and social media accounts. The information is then utilised by AI to create and deliver audience-relevant content.

3: Objectives of the Study

- * To assess the level of awareness amongst consumers with regards to Artificial Intelligence.
- * To determine the consumer preference with respect to use of Artificial intelligence by companies.
- * To identify whether consumers trust companies using artificial intelligence with their personal information.

4: Scope of the study

This study focuses on consumer behavior and preferences with regards to Artificial Intelligence induced digital marketing. This study also focuses on analyzing consumer awareness with respect to Artificial intelligence and Machine learning induced digital marketing and trust levels of consumers with the companies using these tools and they rely on storing and analyzing consumers information.

5: Research Methodology

- * Source of data collection
Primary Data: Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire.
Secondary Data: Books, journals and web-sites
- * Sample Unit: General Population
- * Sample Size: 139
- * Sampling Technique: Convenient sampling

6: Statement of the Problem

Analysis of consumer behavior and preferences with respect to AI induced digital marketing

7: Sampling Plan

Questionnaires were filled by 139 respondents out of which 82 were females and 57 were males.

8: Hypothesis of the study

Hypothesis 1

H0- Consumers are aware about Artificial intelligence and Machine learning used in digital

marketing

H1- Consumers are not aware about Artificial intelligence and Machine learning used in digital marketing

Hypothesis 2

H0- Consumers find Artificial intelligence and Machine learning useful while online shopping
 H1- Consumers do not find Artificial intelligence and Machine learning useful while online shopping

Hypothesis 3

H0- Consumers are comfortable with companies storing their personal information to be utilized for Artificial intelligence induced digital marketing

H1- Consumers are not comfortable with companies storing their personal information to be utilized for Artificial intelligence induced digital marketing

9: Data analysis and interpretation

9A: Gender

The questionnaire was administered by 139 respondents out of which 82 are females which constitute 59 % and 57 respondents are males which is around 41%.

9B: Age

The questionnaire was administered by 139 respondents. Age distribution is shown in the above diagram.

9C: How often have you searched for a product on some shopping website and then later seen ads of the same product while browsing

or while using other platforms like instagram?

The questionnaire was administered by 139 respondents out of which 92 respondents have experienced customized marketing frequently, 40 respectively have experienced it occasionally and 7 have never experienced customized marketing.

9D: Are you aware of a phenomenon called customized marketing in online shopping which uses Artificial intelligence and machine learning?

The questionnaire was administered by 139 respondents out of which 99 respondents are aware about Artificial intelligence induced digital marketing and 40 respondents are not aware about it. Since more people are aware about Artificial intelligence and Machine learning induced digital marketing, null hypothesis is accepted.

9E: When you experience customized marketing. Does your urge to buy the product increase?

The questionnaire was administered by 139 respondents out of which 96 respondents

mentioned that their urge to buy product increases if they experience customized marketing and 43 respondents did not experience any increase in urge to buy the product.

9F: When you experience customized marketing. Are you likely to spend more?

The questionnaire was administered by 139 respondents out of which 82 respondents feel that they are likely to spend more when they experience customized marketing and 51 respondents feel that it has no effect on their spending.

9G: Do you feel that customized marketing is useful to you as a consumer?

The questionnaire was administered by 139 respondents out of which 117 feel that customized marketing is useful to them as consumers and 22 respondents feel that it has no use. Null hypothesis is accepted.

9H: Have you interacted with a chatbot on any website? If Yes, were they able to resolve your issue?

The questionnaire was administered by

139 respondents out of which 53 respondents have interacted with a chatbot and their issue was resolved. 36 respondents have interacted with a chatbot but their issue was not resolved and 53 respondents have never interacted with a chatbot.

9I: Between a chatbot and a human, what would you prefer?

The questionnaire was administered by 139 respondents out of which 124 preferred a human for interaction and 15 respondents preferred a chatbot.

9J: Are you ok with websites storing your personal data to provide you with a better shopping experience using Artificial Intelligence?

The questionnaire was administered by 139 respondents, out of which 94 respondents had no problem with companies storing their personal information for the purpose of Artificial induced digital marketing and 45 respondents mentioned this as invasion of privacy. Null hypothesis is accepted.

10: Conclusion

From the above findings we can conclude that customers are well aware about the use of Artificial intelligence and Machine learning in digital marketing so that companies can provide efficient services to their customers. Customers are also finding it useful since they only see results that are customized for them. Custom-

ers are also comfortable with companies storing their personal data for this purpose. Companies are advised first to have proper disclosure and secondly to store data responsibly as data breach and hacking are very common nowadays.

11: Limitation

A: Study is performed in Mumbai city, therefore geographic limitation exists, generalization of results is possible in this case.

B: If this study is extended to other cities a more accurate analysis is possible.

C: 47.5% respondents are between the age of 15 and 25, therefore even distribution of age would have helped in a better analysis.

D: This particular topic is fairly vast and more research is needed to form any concrete opinion.

12: Suggestions

A: Companies should use artificial intelligence and machine learning to provide customers with a customized experience as customers are aware about it and are also comfortable with it.

B: Companies should make sure that the data they are capturing is minimum and they are keeping it secured.

C: Companies should keep provision of both chatbots and humans to provide customers with a better experience.

D: While online shopping we should exercise caution as the urge to spend is more in case artificial intelligence is used.

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A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON ATTITUDES OF ASSISTANT PROFESSORS OF DEGREE COLLEGES TOWARDS RESEARCH IN SOCIAL SCIENCE

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1. Introduction:

What is social science research? This is not an easy question and there are no simple, authoritative answers since social science research has been defined in many, sometimes conflicting, ways. But it is an important one, because whatever one says about social science research must be premised on this delineation. Social science research-although social inquiry would be a more appropriate term-as used throughout this book, refers to any scientific study of human action and interaction focusing on elements of thought and behavior that are in some sense social. As such, social scientists aspire to science. They intend to study human action and interaction and thought and behavior in systematic, rigorous, evidence-based, generalizing, replicable, and cumulative fashion. Such research is or can be, of great importance to human affairs. Even though some social scientists would dispute this definition, it is, nonetheless, neither too precise not too general and therefore sufficient to define the practice of social research in lucid, cogent way.

That being said,. Social science research